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Meet the Belgian e-driver

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Summary

The market of electric vehicles (EV) is entering a next stage of the product life cycle. E-drivers are no longer the pioneering adventure seekers or very early adopters. In this study, we analyze the profile of current Belgian e-drivers to inform market development decision makers about their characteristics and behaviour, and their needs and wants.

Keywords: charging, market, consumers, infrastructure, BEV

1 Introduction

The market of electric vehicles (EVs), i.e. battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), has grown the last years. In 2018 the global fleet of EVs exceeded 5.1 million. This is an increase of 2 million compared to the previous year and nearly doubling of the number of sales of new EVs [1]. In Belgium currently 63,000 EVs are registered. The BEV/PHEV ratio is approximately 1/2 (BEV: 21,231; PHEV: 41,807). In 2019, the EVs have a market share of 5.1% of newly registered vehicles in Belgium, with 0,7% for BEVs [2]. Of all these registered EVs, approximately 83.17% are registered as company cars [3]. The data of [4], within which the number of vehicles registered per province, show that the Belgian EVs are mainly registered in the province of Antwerp, in the city of Antwerp in particular, as well as in and around Brussels. Furthermore, both BEV and PHEV registrations are located primarily in Flanders and Brussels, with a rather limited share in Wallonia. (The maps with subdivisions of privately owned and company-owned EVs can be found in the appendix.)

Given the growth of the EV market, it is important to gain insight into the characteristics and behaviour of e-drivers. This study contributes to current scientific knowledge about the profile of e-drivers, their behaviour, needs and perceptions. The research question tackled in this paper is as follows:

“What is the profile of the Belgian e-driver in terms of socio-demographic characteristics, mobility behavior, and charging needs and habits?”.

According to previous studies worldwide [5, 6, 7], the EV driver is typically male, 45 years old, well-educated (university education), has a high income, and usually owns more than one car in his household. To put the results about the Belgian e-driver in perspective, we also refer to general statistics about mobility and driving behaviour in Belgium. In 2017, the private Belgian driver drove an average of 41km a day, which is lower compared to company car drivers that drive 78 km a day on average [8].

2 Methodology

This study concerns drivers of a BEV or PHEV in Belgium, described as the Belgian e-drivers. The following characteristics were deemed relevant based on academic literature review and practitioners' insight: socio-demographics, technical knowledge, habits, needs, incentives and mobility behavior, charging behavior in terms of location, frequency and perception of service, interest to participate in V2G, a benchmark to measure technical knowledge and the willingness-to-pay for a faster charging session. The survey was conducted during the summer of 2019 and was available in Dutch and in French. The survey was sent to fleet managers, employees in the possession of an EV and private EV users. With this direct approach, we obtained a high number of responses from all types of sectors, with a different number of driver profiles within the company, in terms of age, education and function. The analysis is based on 310 fully completed surveys, mainly by e-drivers of a BEV (72.6%) or a PHEV (23.5%). 3.9% of the respondents are in the possession of an EV with a range extender.

3 Results

This section presents the preliminary analysis of the sample. Of the surveyed Belgian e-drivers, 87.7% are male and 12.3% are female. The average respondent is 46 years old and has a university degree. Furthermore, the survey was mainly completed by fully employed people with jobs in middle management or self-employed respondents. The average household in the survey consists of a family of 3 or more who lives in a detached house, with a combined net monthly income of between 3,000 and 5,000 euros. Within the household, the EV is the main car (i.e. vehicle with highest kilometres travelled a year).

Figure 1: Respondents per municipality. Visualization by MOBI.

Spatial analysis reveals that the respondents mainly live in and around the capital of Brussels, in the city of Antwerp and, to a lesser extent, spread throughout Flanders and Wallonia. 46.5% of the Belgian e-drivers are employed in a small company (1-49 employees), 15.2% in a mid-sized company (50-500) and 38.4% in a large company (more than 500 employees). These companies are mainly active in the Information & Communication (21.3%), the service (20.0%) and the IT sector (14.2%).

3.1 Mobility Behaviour

With 95% certainty, the Belgian e-driver drives daily between 81.8 km and 99.3 km (mean: 90.6 min: 0.0 max: 687.0 median: 70.0). Compared to [3] this is a high number, and that might be due to the large share of company cars in our survey (81.9%). The respondents indicated that, in addition to commuting, the car is often used for customer and company visits. 41.9% of the respondents drive a car that is less than one year old.

When looking at the popularity of brands and models, it is clear that Tesla is by far the most popular brand: 45.8% of EVs and 63.1% of BEV's. The next pursuer is the Nissan LEAF with a share of 13.8%. In the PHEVs segment, BMW is the main player with a share of 9.7% of the respondents (35.3% of all PHEVs). As a result of the high share of Tesla's, the average EV has a battery capacity of more than 70 kWh, and a driving range of between 300 and 400 km.

In terms of use, on average, the EV is parked at home for a substantial part of the day, with a 95% certainty between 13.2h and 14.4h a day (mean: 13.8 h; min: 0; max: 24; median: 13), as shown in table 1. In addition, the EV is parked about 6 hours in the employer's car park and the Belgian e-driver is on the road for about 2 hours a day. The EV only spends a small part of the day parked at a public or other car parks.

Table 1: Daily use of EV (in h)

	Mean	Median	CI (95%)
Parked at home	13.82	13	[13.2; 14.4]
Parked in an employer's car park	6.07	8	[5.5; 6.6]
On the road	2.03	2	[1.8; 2.2]
Parked in a public car park/public car park	1.24	0	[0.8; 1.7]
Parked in other places	0.83	0	[0.6; 1.1]

Overall, the EV is used for all kinds of daily activities (table 2). Commuter travel is the main reason for using the EV, which is not surprising since most (81.9%) of them are company cars. The car is also frequently used for leisure activities and private errands.

Table 2: Use of EV

Use of EV	Survey sample
Commuter travel	90.7%
For leisure activities (e.g. visiting relatives and friends, cultural events, shopping/strolling, sports/club, day trip).	88.6%
For private errands (e.g. purchase, doctor visit, administration, dropping off/picking up children, care for relatives).	87.1%
For holiday trips	66.1%

Table 3 summarises the most important information about the average Belgian EV.

Table 3: Average Belgian EV

Average Belgian EV	
Daily distance	90.6km
Company owned	81.9%
Battery capacity	+70kWh
Driving range	300-400km
Tesla's share of the BEVs	63.1%
Daily use of EV	81.6%

The respondents indicate that environmental awareness is the most important reason for using an EV (50.0% of the respondents). This is reinforced by the fact that the Belgian e-driver mainly identifies low emissions (26.5%) and fuel efficiency (20.0%) as the main reasons for purchasing/leasing an EV (Table

4). Other reasons for choosing and using an EV are driving pleasure and the fact that it is innovative and hip to own an EV. The Belgian e-driver shows a strong ecological awareness. A large share of e-drivers (50.6%) own photovoltaic (PV) solar panels at home.

Table 4: Top 5 reasons for buying/using EV

Top 5 reasons for purchase EV	Top 5 reasons for use of EV
Fuel efficiency	Ecological reasons
Low emissions	Driving pleasure
Comfort	Innovative, hip
Safety measures	More efficient vehicle technology
Performance	Tax advantageous reason

3.2 Charging behaviour

This study surveyed when, where and how often the respondents charge their EV. 54.5% of the respondents charge it on a daily base. As can be seen in figure 2, a major part of the EVs are charged daily at home (45.1%) (e.g. private charging station (23.5%) and power socket (21.6%) or at a private charging station at work (24.2%).

Figure 2: Frequency for different charging locations.

In addition, the charging profile of respondents that charge daily at home at a private charging station (23.5% of the respondents, n=73) is compared with the respondents that charge daily at work (24.2% of the respondents, n=75).

Home charging (see the blue line in Figure 3) is mainly done after working hours, between 8PM and 6AM. This is also due to the fact that the EV is parked at home for between 13.2h and 14.4h. Respondents who charge at work on a daily basis (see the orange line in Figure 3) do this largely between 8AM and 4PM, after which they continue to charge their vehicles at home after 8PM.

Overall, charging (gray line in Figure 2) is in decline from the morning onwards, before picking up again in the evening.

Figure 3: Time of day when the EV is charged.

The usage of public charging stations is affected by waiting times, i.e. the time before an occupied charging station becomes available again. Most e-drivers (59.3%) never wait at a public charging station and about a third (30.3%) indicates that they are willing to wait a maximum of 15 minutes before an occupied charging station is available.

Table 5: Waiting time before an occupied charging station becomes available.

Waiting time for availability charging station	Survey sample
15 minutes or less	31.2%
More than 15 minutes but not more than 30 minutes	5.7%
More than 30 minutes but not more than 1 hour	2.5%
More than 1 hour	2.5%
I never wait when a charging point is occupied	58.1%

3.2.1 Ideal charging session

The most important characteristic of an ideal charging session is the connection time (59.4% rank this characteristic at the top) as there is a clear demand to shorten the charging session. The second most important aspect of an ideal charging session is a short waiting time for the availability of the charging station (44.5%). Most e-drivers never wait for a charging station to be available (as can be seen in Table 5). Instead, most e-drivers will look for an available charging station rather than waiting at an occupied one. A last important characteristic is the interoperability of the charging pass. A substantial number of users (40.9%) attach value to the interoperability of the charging pass in regard to the charging session. Less important determinants for an ideal charging station are surrounding activities like a place to drink or eat something (24.2%) or offering an integrated cable (17.3%).

3.2.2 Willingness-to-pay fast charging

In order to assess the willingness to pay for fast charging, respondents were presented with a scenario: *“It is early afternoon, your electric car still has a range of 20km on the counter and in the evening, you have an appointment at 150km from your current location. You are completely dependent on public charging infrastructure that day, so you drive to a charging station. There you can choose between two charging points, the first requiring 4 hours of charging and the second 20 minutes of charging (300km in total).”*

Based on this scenario, 79.6% of the respondents were willing to pay more if the charging time was substantially reduced. In the end, the Belgian e-driver is willing to pay with 95% certainty between 19.6 and 22.3 euros for the proposed scenario (20 minutes of charging for 300 km of driving range). Furthermore, it is remarkable that in our data Tesla drivers are willing to pay more (on average 22.0 euros) than non-Tesla drivers (on average 20.3 euros).

3.2.3 Interest in Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)

In addition to the current perception of the Belgian e-driver, this section focuses on the user’s perception of new charging techniques. It provides insights to what extent the Belgian e-driver is aware of innovative technologies.

In the current study, the greater part of the sample (71.3%) has heard of V2G-technology. More specifically, approximately half (48.7%) is already quite familiar with V2G. No less than 72.9% of Belgian e-drivers are interested in buying a car with V2G technology after having obtained this information about V2G. According to the Belgian e-drivers, the most important conditions for the willingness-to-participate in V2G are (1) residential energy services, which enable the e-driver to use his or her car as a source of energy for his household; (2) sufficient V2G charging infrastructure is available, which is in line with the current concern about available charging infrastructure [9]; and (3) a similar purchase price to their current EV.

3.3 Comparative analyses

In this section, we focus on the comparative analyses in terms of age, car ownership, profession and the differences between car brands.

3.3.1 Age profiles

Three groups were distinguished according to their age: Belgian e-drivers younger than 35 (13.2%, n=41), between 35 and 55 (69.7%, n=216), and older than 55 (17.1%, n=53).

When looking at the charging behaviour per age profile as depicted in Figure 4, it can be seen that people from profile 1 (younger than 35, the blue line) mainly charge during work hours, which is not the case for the other profiles. For profiles 2 (aged between 35 and 55, the orange line) and 3 (older than 55, the gray line), residential charging is mainly carried out at night (after 8 PM).

Figure 4: Charging behavior EV users per age profile.

There is also a difference in terms of the daily kilometers driven. The Belgian e-drivers in profile 1 (younger than 35) travel remarkably longer distances compared to the other age profiles (Table 6).

Table 6: Distance travelled (in km): age profiles

	Mean	Median	CI (95%)
Profile 1: -35y	101.0	80	[73.6; 128.3]
Profile 2: 35-55y	93.7	70	[80.5; 106.9]
Profile 3: +55y	84.9	65	[69.4; 100.5]

If the reasons for using and purchasing an EV among the age profiles are compared, a similar ranking is found for profile 1 and profile 2, with fuel efficiency and low emissions as the most important reasons. In the case of profile 3, a greater importance is attached to comfort (Table 7).

Table 7: Top 5 reasons for purchase EV

Profile 1 (-35y)	Profile 2 (35-55y)	Profile 3 (+55y)
Fuel efficiency	Fuel efficiency	Comfort
Low emissions	Low emissions	Fuel efficiency
Comfort	Comfort	Low emissions
Safety measures	Safety measures	Performance
Performance	Performance	Safety measures

When comparing the types of cars, the share of BEVs is more or less the same. We notice that 73.2% of the people in profile 1 are in possession of BEVs, compared to 72.7% of the people in profile 2 and

71.7% of profile 3. Tesla is well represented with a share of more than 68.2% of BEVs in profile 2, 55.3% in profile 3 and with a little less than half (46.7%) in profile 1. The second most popular BEV is the Nissan LEAF with a share of respectively 17% in profile 1 and 19% in profile 3.

3.3.2 Privately-owned vs company-owned

As indicated above, the data set used in this study shows that the majority of EVs are company-owned (81.9%). Within this subgroup of company-owned cars, 39.4% of the e-drivers are self-employed. Socio-demographically, 7.2% of privately-owned e-drivers are retired (in comparison with company-owned: 1.9%). The e-drivers who own the car privately are on average 3 years older than those with a company car.

An important difference with respect to the type of ownership can be noticed in the share of BEVs. The share of BEVs in households owning a private EV is 94.6%, which is much higher than the share of BEVs for households owning a company-owned EV (67.7%). A privately owned EV is more often (28.6%) the only car in the household compared to the company car (15.7%). This can be explained by the fact that the number of people in households that own an EV privately is lower. These households are mainly without children in this sample.

Table 8: Distance travelled (in km): private vs company

	Mean	Median	CI (95%)
Privately-owned	70.7	52	[54.8; 86.5]
Company-owned	98.1	80	[86.3; 109.9]

Despite the fact that the distribution in terms of battery capacity is more or less the same in both profiles, it is noteworthy that 15.4% of the respondents with a company car do not know the battery capacity of their car, compared to 3.6% for e-drivers with a private car. In addition, 37.4% of e-drivers with a company car estimate their maximum achieved distance to be lower than the Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicle Testing Procedure (WLTP) of their car, compared to 26.0% of e-driver with a private car. This, combined with the knowledge on battery capacity, might indicate that the e-driver with a privately owned EV is better informed. Not surprisingly, the company car is used more frequently for commuting compared to the privately-owned car. This is also noticeable in the daily distance travelled (Table 8). Indeed, the distance travelled is almost 30 km higher for company cars (98.1 km) than for privately owned cars (70.7 km).

Table 9: Reasons for use EV: company vs private

Reasons for use EV	Company-owned	Privately-owned
Ecological reasons	82.3%	85.7%
Driving pleasure	70.9%	82.1%
Financial incentives	62.6%	28.6%
Innovative, hip	55.5%	58.9%
More efficient vehicle technology in terms of energy consumption	53.5%	73.2%
Acceleration capacity	39.0%	42.9%

Concerning the purchase decision of an EV, the low operating and maintenance costs are clearly seen as a more important factor for privately-owned cars (ranked 2nd) than for company-owned cars (ranked 4th). On the other hand, the choice of financial incentives is considerably greater for company cars, where 62.6% indicated that this was a reason for the use of an EV (Table 9), compared to privately owned cars, where 28.6% of the respondents indicated that this was a reason for using the EV. This can possibly be explained by the tax advantages.

Respondents with a privately owned EV deliberately chose an EV brand and model. That is not always the case for company car owners, yet roughly less than half (47.2%) of the respondents with a company-owned car indicated that they would make the same choice if they had to buy the car themselves.

In terms of charging habits, there is also a remarkable difference as the majority of e-drivers with a private car (42.9%) wait up to 30 minutes at a charging station, which is higher compared to e-drivers

Figure 5: Charging locations privately owned EVs.

with a company owned car (33.8%). Moreover, 60.6% of e-drivers with a company car never wait for an occupied charging station, where 51.8% of the respondents with a private EV never wait. Subsequently, e-drivers with a private car charge mainly at home (62.5%) with a frequency of several days a week (28.6% of respondents with a private car charge daily at a private charging station at home). This is much more in comparison with e-drivers with a company car, where 45.6% charge several times a weeks at a private charging station at home (22.4% daily). On the other side, more than half of the company owned EVs (58.2%) charge several times a week on a private charging station at work, which is twice as high as the e-drivers with an EV in private possession (19.7%).

Figure 6: Charging locations company owned EVs.

Lastly, e-drivers with a company car charge more often (38.2%) in the morning, after they arrive at work, stop charging in a constant decrease until the end of the working day, just to reprise it when they come home at 8pm. Whereas people who own a private car charge mainly at night at home (57.4%), then have a relapse during working hours to charge in the afternoon until they leave work to charge after 8PM.

Figure 7: Time of day when the EV is charged: private vs company.

3.3.3 Housing

In this study, 86% of the respondents live in a house (56.5% detached house, 19.4% semi-detached house and 11.3% terraced house), 12.8% lives in an apartment. More than half, 55.3% of the e-drivers who live in an apartment charge at home on a daily basis (39.5% at a private charge point and 15.8% at the power socket; see figure 7), compared to 42.1% of e-drivers living in a house (see figure 8). This can be explained by the fact that 100% of the e-drivers who live in an apartment privately own the EV. This implies that e-drivers who live in an apartment mainly charge after working hours (figure 9). Concerning the charging time at the location of the employer, 26.7% of the e-drivers who live in a house charge daily during working hours (Figure 8), in comparison to 15.8% of e-drivers who live in an apartment.

Figure 8: Charging behaviour apartment.

Figure 9: Charging behaviour house.

Figure 10: Daily charging behaviour: house vs apartment.

3.3.4 Are Tesla owners different from the other EV owners?

Since 45.8% of the respondents are driving a Tesla (63.1% of BEVs) it is interesting to compare this profile with the other e-drivers (other BEVs) as well. Tesla drivers travel considerably more kilometers (109.5km) in one day than the drivers of other brands (BEV) (82.0km), as can be seen in Table 10.

Table 10: Distance travelled (in km): tesla vs non-Tesla

	Mean	Median	CI (95%)
Tesla	109.5	100	[94.2; 124.7]
Non-Tesla	82	70	[66.5; 97.4]

The Tesla driver also has a higher income (figure 10). About half (51.4%) of the Tesla users have a net income of more than 5000 euros, this share is about twice as high as the share of non-Tesla users with this income (26.5%). A majority of non-Tesla users (55.4%), have a net income between 3000 euros and 4999 euros. The recent rise of EVs, and the growing number of models on the market is noticeable in the profile of non-Tesla owners as these cars are owned by the e-driver for less than 1 year. For Tesla drivers, there is an equilibrium between cars younger than 1 year and cars with an age of 2 years. It is noteworthy that almost half (44%) of non-Tesla BEV drivers charge several days a week up to daily at a home socket. This compared to only 25% for Tesla drivers. That Tesla is a popular company car is especially noticeable in the self-employed and the liberal professions, where no less than 82.9% of the self-employed who own a BEV drive a Tesla.

Figure 11: Net wages Tesla and non-Tesla owners.

4 Conclusion & discussion

In this paper, an answer has been formulated to the research question: “*What is the profile of the Belgian e-driver anno 2019 in terms of socio-demographic characteristics, mobility behavior, and charging needs and habits?*”. Generally, the Belgian e-driver is male, 46 years old and in possession of a university degree, lives in a household consisting of 3 people, and lives in and around the capital of Brussels. This is in line with previous findings [5, 6], where the average e-driver is mainly male, 45+ and highly educated. The Belgian e-driver can be described as a ‘car lover’. Indeed, 65.8% would be described through this term by family and friends and driving pleasure is one of the main reasons for the use of the EV. Furthermore, it appears that the main reasons for purchasing and using the EV are ecological reasons, such as fuel efficiency and low emissions. The importance of these topics was identified [10, 6] as the main motivations of EV-adaptation.

The EV is the main car for 67.4% of the respondents, i.e. the car with the highest annual mileage in the household. On average, the Belgian e-driver travels 90.6 km per day, which is considerably higher than the the distance an average Belgian car travels on a daily basis [8]. The average daily distance of a Belgian company car compared to the distance of the electric company car ($M=101.0\text{km}$) is substantially higher ($M=78.0\text{km}$) [8]. The results of this study show that 42% of the cars are in possession by the

current driver for less than 1 year. The respondent fleet consisted of 73.8% BEVs, 22.6% PHEVs and 3.6% Range extender. In Belgium, the BEV/PHEV ratio is currently 1/2 [2].

In terms of charging behaviour, the e-driver charges mainly at home (in the evening) and at work (during the day). 54.5% of the respondents charge on a daily based. If this is subdivided between house and apartment, 55.2% of the people living in a house charge daily. This is not much different from results [11] which indicate that 59% of e-drivers living in a house charge daily. When looking at e-drivers living in an apartment, 50% charge daily. This is a big difference with the results of [11] where 12% of people living in an apartment charge daily. It is remarkable that 33.9% indicate that they never charge at work, which is below the 50% of [11].

71.3% of Belgian e-drivers are interested in buying a car with V2G technology. The most important conditions for the willingness-to-participate in V2G: residential energy services, which enable the e-driver to use his or her car as a source of energy for his household; a sufficient availability of V2G charging infrastructure; and a similar purchase price to their current EV. This is in line with the study [9] about the concerns of charging infrastructure.

Regarding the difference between company owned and privately owned EVs, 81.9% of the cars are owned by a company/leasing company. Of these company owned cars, 70% are BEVs, of which 86% are Tesla cars. Of the remaining 16.5% privately owned EVs, almost the entire sample consists of BEVs (93.5%). 48.5% of the e-drivers with a company-owned car indicated that they would make the same choice if they had to buy the car themselves. Furthermore, the results on technical knowledge show that a private e-driver has more technical knowledge about his car.

The notable results between the different age profiles are mainly the distances, where profile 1 (younger than 35) travels considerably more km compared to the other profiles. Also, it appears that the e-drivers in profile 1 are much less aware of the technical characteristics of their car. Lastly, looking into the reasons for using an EV, the e-drivers in profile 3 (older than 55) attach great importance to comfort.

Tesla drivers, with a 64% share in this data set, have a more powerful battery, which reduces the need for charging. In addition, they also cover a greater distance every day. A remarkable difference can be found in the willingness-to-pay for fast charging infrastructure, where non-Tesla drivers are more willing to pay than Tesla drivers. 86% of the respondents live in a house and 14% lives in an apartment. 55.3% of the e-drivers who live in an apartment charge at home on a daily, compared to 42.1% of e-drivers living in a house. This can be explained by the fact that all the e-drivers who are living in an apartment privately own the EV. Almost 30% of the e-drivers living in a house charge daily at the charging point at work, compared to 15% of the e-drivers who live in an apartment. Remarkably, despite the fact that the majority (89.6%) does not wait or waits no longer than 15 minutes at an occupied charging station, the waiting time at an occupied charging station is indicated as one of the main characteristics of an ideal charging session. As indicated in [12], waiting time is one of the most annoying experiences for an e-driver. The ideal charging session is further described as a short connection time and a good interoperability of the charging pass. Which is, still today, one of the indicated problems concerning charging experiences [9]. It is also interesting to know that almost half of the Belgian e-drivers own PV solar panels.

Limitations of this study are the sampling strategy and sample size. Despite our efforts to widely distribute the survey and given the lack of official data about EV owners, the sample might not be fully representative for the e-driver population in Belgian. Future work includes the study of the different segments of e-drivers in more detail.

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